
SKETCH OF A NOVEL APPROACH TO A NEURAL MODEL

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we lay out a novel model of neuroplasticity in the form of a horizontal-vertical integration model of neural processing. We believe a new approach to neural modeling will benefit the 'third wave' of AI. The 'horizontal' plane consists of an adaptive network of neurons connected by transmission links which generates spatio-temporal spike patterns. This fits with standard computational neuroscience approaches. Additionally, for each individual neuron, there is a 'vertical' part consisting of internal adaptive parameters steering the external, membrane-expressed parameters which are involved in neural transmission. Each neuron has a vertical modular system of parameters, corresponding to (a) external parameters at the membrane layer, divided into compartments (spines, boutons), (b) internal parameters in the submembrane zone and the cytoplasm with its intracellular protein signaling network, and (c) 'core' parameters in the nucleus for genetic and epigenetic information. In such models, each node (=neuron) in the horizontal network has its own internal memory. Neural transmission and information storage are systematically separated, an important conceptual advance over synaptic weight models. We discuss the membrane-based ('external') filtering and selection of outside signals for processing vs. signal loss by fast fluctuations and the neuron-internal computing strategies from intracellular protein signaling to the nucleus as the 'core' system. We want to show that the individual neuron has an important role in the computation of signals, and that many assumptions derived from the synaptic weight adjustment hypothesis of memory may not hold in a real brain. Not every transmission event leaves a trace, and the neuron is a self-programming device, rather than passively determined by current input. Ultimately we strive to build a flexible memory system that processes facts and events automatically.

There is room on the inside.

1 Introduction: The neuron as a system with internal and external parameters

Experimental research on neurons, and as a consequence theoretical analysis, is often divided into electrophysiology and molecular biology. The first deals with membrane potentials, spikes and activations in networks of neurons linked via synapses, the second deals with intracellular signaling, genetic networks, release of neuromodulators, receptors, ion channels, transporters and various processes linked to this. In both cases we are aware of signal-induced plasticity, but an understanding of neural plasticity concurrently on the levels of electrophysiology in neural networks (horizontal plane) and the molecular interactions in single neurons (vertical interactions) is missing.

The master framework linking observations on neural plasticity is focused on associative synaptic plasticity, usually in the form of long-term potentiation or depression [61, 18, 54, 77, 57, 107]. Interesting and relevant criticisms and alternative suggestions are contained in [7, 8, 55, 100, 3, 32]. Here we analyze experimental results from a primarily agnostic perspective, with the goal of finding an adequate functional description and asking for the utility of an appropriately designed neuron model. Already, complex dynamic models of intracellular signaling [9, 42, 20] and

genetic read-out [17, 56, 10] exist as well as elaborate simulation models [89]. However, simulation models attempt to match actual biological processes precisely, accordingly they model only very small parts of systems in an attempt to model them with high accuracy. But here, we are not interested in that. Instead, we want to raise the question how the neuron is organized as a complex system, how it processes and stores information, and how this applies to computational models.

In a first approach, we suggest to model membrane properties by a set of external parameters, localized at the synapse, the spine (where it exists), the soma, the dendrite or the axonal bouton. External parameters respond to signals from the outside, but they are also guided and controlled by submembrane processes, which we describe by internal parameters. While external parameters influence neural transmission properties which are visible to other neurons, internal parameters only have indirect effects on neural transmission and remain hidden from other neurons. Together external and internal parameters form the 'processing layer' or the upper part of the 'vertical' system of neural plasticity. In contrast, the nucleus contains core parameters, both epigenetic (histones) and genetic (DNA) which respond to internal signaling. This provides another layer of depth for processing information and long-term memory. Core parameters receive and send information to the internal parameters via the nuclear membrane. In this paper, they will not be analysed in detail.

Neural networks were developed to derive functional models from ideas about neural interactions. In contrast, for internal cellular models, such as biochemical reaction systems and genetic transcription networks, dynamical systems approaches are often used. While neural networks are suitable for computation, but highly inaccurate for detailed biological simulation, dynamical systems models are unwieldy for computation, subject to dependence on small parameter changes and only suitable for small-scale simulation models. Without further elaboration [19] these models are also highly incompatible. They do not focus on the task of information processing that we want to analyze. Therefore we tentatively describe the systems of submembrane and cytoplasmic intracellular signaling [12] and their properties by amorphous internal parameters, to be elaborated later [47].

Our goal must be to isolate information processing from complex cellular computation, since the neuronal cell performs this in the wider context of all cell-internal mechanisms. Therefore we suggest to operate with the very general abstraction of high-level functional parameters instead. This could be augmented at later times with more precisely defined types of parameters or interactions on the basis of mathematical models. Our first goal in this paper will be to investigate what insights we can gain from this point of view.

External parameters, roughly corresponding to membrane proteins, respond to outside signals undergo plasticity on at least three time-scales: fast (milliseconds, desensitization), intermediate (seconds-minutes, endocytosis, insertion), and slow (hours, new proteins or morphological features like spines). Only the fast responses which usually involve protein conformational changes do not require the participation of the internal, vertical processing system. Both the reversible endocytosis of membrane proteins, and the long-term ubiquitination of proteins or generation of new proteins require a complex system of internal interactions.

The set of internal parameters corresponding to intracellular signaling is the first line in orchestrating the plasticity of external parameters. This imposes onto the response to outside signals an internal generative model of membrane properties [73]. This is a very important point. It means that within a neural ensemble, synaptic and membrane plasticity is not only and directly dependent on the signals that are passed among the neurons. Instead the activity of the intracellular protein signaling system is necessary for selecting and responding to signals [73, 5]. The behavior of the neuron cannot be determined from observation of the signals it receives. Rather, adaptation is a combination of the stored model and new information.

Membrane-near control structures such as spines contain hundreds of protein species which interact to orchestrate membrane protein position and efficacy [27, 52]. The intracellular system contains spatially distributed parts in distinct positions (e.g. at dendritic spines, axonal boutons) and a central 'workspace' in the form of the cytoplasm with its organelles and protein complexes.

The membrane with its many inserted proteins, such as ion channels, receptors, transporters etc. influences neural transmission, i.e. the horizontal interactions between neurons. It is compartmentalized at dendrites into branches/spines/synapses, and at axons into branches and axonal boutons. Outside signals are therefore received on a highly structured surface, such that, although neighboring interactions exist, signals can be located by origin, and are processed in a spatially highly distributed way. Synaptic signals received at the membrane are brief (milliseconds), and potentially repeating. Synaptic signals typically produce calcium transients from NMDA receptors and voltage-gated calcium channels (VGCCs), as well as calcium buffering proteins and calcium release from internal stores [45, 37]. There is evidence that calcium is a major signal for the induction of plasticity and that different shapes of the signal result in different outcomes [75]. There are also signals, like neuromodulators, which have longer durations, on the order of seconds, or even minutes. The short-term external parameter response is governed by outside signals, such as

receptor ligands, but longer duration responses require the selection and filtering of membrane signals by the internal system.

The innermost module is the nucleus, which has DNA as permanent storage for protein information, and an epigenetic histone system which codes for the accessibility of DNA [48]. Signals are accumulated and integrated, temporally and spatially before being sent to the central core. Phosphorylations or methylations which are performed by proteins in a reversible manner code for easy access to genes. Signals pass from the cytoplasm to the nucleus usually in the form of proteins which are transcription factors activating coordinating sets of genes. Thus whole genetic programs can be started such as morphological growth of spines, axons, or dendrites. Individual genes (e.g. AMPA receptors) may also be transcribed during periods of neural plasticity based on histone accessibility [48].

One task of the processing layer is to take a spatially distributed, temporally structured signal and produce a spatially centralized, temporally integrated signal of transcription factors to cause DNA read-out of individual genes or genetic programs. This is not a simple task. Signals are selected near the membrane, they are shaped and re-structured in time, and they need to be sorted or transferred to protein complexes in the cytoplasm and ultimately activate proteins which enter into the nucleus. In the nucleus, epigenetic adaptation regulates access to DNA and also serves the function of considerable noise reduction, channeling signals by enhancement and suppression. It is clear then that signals from the periphery have to be processed on several levels, and with several types of control structures before they can actually be used to control or regulate DNA read-out, or be stored in the epigenetic layer around it.

The other task of the internal parameter system in the membrane-near processing layer is to enact short-term plasticity and directly shape external membrane expression on the basis of existing information (i.e. a generative model). Signals from the environment occur fast and they are ordered in time. When they arrive at the membrane, they are being transformed at the membrane layer through internal parameters in feedback cycles and similar control structures. These can suppress, lengthen, or augment a signal by engaging the intracellular signaling network. The result is new external membrane expression as a combination of the stored generative model for external parameter response and incoming, possibly adaptive information.

In this context, it is interesting that the intracellular system itself is devoid of memory, and cannot respond to signals by adaptive plasticity or regulate its own plasticity [24, 94, 11]. There is temporal integration for membrane signals, and temporally orchestrated intracellular responses, such as G protein- mediated signaling by small molecules [] or the kinase/phosphatase system [46]. But the system properties can only be changed by altering the abundances of proteins via mRNA translation, which takes hours to be reset and recalculated. This observation strengthens the view of the internal parameter system as a processing layer, programmable by signals from the outside and updated from inside via parameter re-sets such as local mRNA translation and the core DNA transcription system.

To summarize, the membrane layer is adaptive on several time scales, in the long term by genetic read-out. Under certain conditions, protein abundances in the processing layer or at the membrane may change, adapting the neuron to a new environment. This shows that associative synaptic plasticity, such as long-term potentiation / depression (LTP/LTD) can be seen as a special case of signal-induced long-term membrane plasticity.

2 Signal Selection and Filtering

In our conceptual model, parameters stand for proteins/molecules, sometimes for groups of them, or variants of the same molecule. (A precise matching of parameters to biochemistry is not intended at this point, but this is a step that can always be added.) The values for these parameters – both external, at the membrane, and internal, near the membrane, or localized somewhere in the cytosol – change by computations or by outside signals. Outside signals are first sensed by external parameters, they are processed with the help of internal parameters, i.e. filtered or selected, stored or dropped. In response to signals, external parameters may return to their values (homeostatic regulation) or they may be re-set to new values (adaptive regulation).

Outside signals are at first pre-processed by external parameters (receptors and indirectly ion channels) at the membrane. Immediate, reversible plasticity of receptors and ligand-gated ion channels usually by protein conformational changes constitutes the first response. Calcium and small molecules, like cAMP, as well as the kinase/phosphatase system engage the internal parameter system. Control structures and computations by internal parameters decide about the fate of signals (cf. Fig. 1).

The membrane has a strong tendency towards homeostasis, i.e. return to existing values, after short-term disruption. But in some situations, the accumulation of traces from each signaling event is predominant. Whether a signal is eliminated and ignored, or passed on to submembrane zones and intracellular protein signaling, does not just depend on the signal, but also on the responsiveness of the neuron. From a theoretical perspective we are dealing with a problem of feature (=signal) selection and feature construction for learning and memory [38]. The signal may have a higher chance if it

Figure 1: Filtering and selection of signals at the membrane. External signals are created from outside signals which are interpreted by external parameters. If they pass the "filter", they are transformed by the internal parameter set into internal signals.

is either strong (high amplitude, co-occurring at various sites), or repeating (at the same sites), or long-lasting (even at a lower level of signaling). In general we may assume, (a) that even fairly weak signals can be retained, if signals combine within a specified time frame, and if the neuron is highly responsive and (b) even strong signals fail to register, if the neuron has low responsivity, and if the signal is isolated. These questions have to be explored further from the perspective of utility (which feature selection processes are most useful) and experimentally (effect of responsivity, along the lines of [108, 73, 23]).

There are several models possible for the integration of the external with the internal parameter system. For instance, we may assume that external parameters fluctuate, they follow a random walk and are reinforced by internal parameters. Such a model could emulate modern feature selection methods [38] very effectively. Another approach is that external parameters are corrected by values from the internal parameters, which would amount to supervised learning, or that the internal parameter system only selectively augments the external parameters by stored default values.

Calcium modulation has often been indicated as a major factor in initiating plasticity (ref). The shape of the calcium transients, where strong high-amplitude calcium transients directly permeate into intracellular signaling to begin to make changes [26, 64, 30] matters, indicating a preference for brief, strong signals. Calcium enters the cell via various ion channels and receptors, there are intracellular calcium buffers, and mechanisms for release from intracellular stores, such that the factors influencing calcium transients are an example for the integration of outside signals and internal parameters.

Another factor influencing signal selection based on external-internal integration is neuromodulation (NM) via G-protein coupled receptors (GPCRs) [93]. G proteins are internally connected to ion channels which they regulate. The NM-ion channel complex determines the excitability of the neuron conditional on which (central) NM signal modulates it. NM-ion channel interactions can do reversible dendrite remodeling at intermediate time frames. This means that the different NMs highlight the set of neurons that are modulated by them [81]. In this regard we may hypothesize that low-frequency neurons ('naive neurons') are dominated by a single NM, and only few, high-frequency 'hub' neurons have acquired noticeable responses to several NMs, imposing an activation scheme onto a neuronal ensemble, where hubs are preferentially modulated.

Outside signals to a neuron have the potential to activate certain proteins as immediate early genes (e.g. Arc, CREB) within minutes (5-20 minutes for Arc in hippocampal neurons [39, 40]), which transfer to the nucleus [78, 65]. However, they are transferred by intracellular signaling, with a large number of control structures such as thresholds, feedback loops, feedforward loops, antagonistic signaling [82]. For instance, negative feedback serves to broaden a signal and extend its duration, it may also dampen a signal below threshold. Signals may be modified, such that later signals in a sequence are being suppressed, or a sequence of signals is enhanced to reach a threshold for the processing layer [63]. In this sense, internal control structures serve to adapt a signal and influence whether it is passed on to the next layer.

The point is that these control structures are activated by signals but depend on internal parameters. They may also depend on core parameters or genetic properties. An example is the co-regulation of ion channels [44, 71, 2]. Co-regulation, which requires genetic read-out, shows strong internal bias (genetic conservatism for a neuronal type) and does not require network-based regulation [34, 28]. The neuron itself "knows" its well-balanced state. This makes construction of horizontal models much easier, since each processor element monitors its own stability.

There is a notable difference between spiny and aspiny plasticity, spines being localized at projection neurons in areas of strong adult plasticity, such as pyramidal neurons in cortex, hippocampus and amygdala, medium spiny neurons in striatum and in certain dendritic regions of Purkinje cells in cerebellum - areas of high fine-tuned plasticity. Interestingly, dendritic spines (and possibly axonal boutons) act as cellular compartments with a highly reduced intracellular signaling apparatus [70], showing the value of mechanistic reduction in these cases. In contrast, aspiny neurons have synapses without a dedicated local system of intracellular signalling. This can make a big difference for plasticity where spine removal and generation is an efficient modification of existing information. Aspiny plasticity would then require more substantial remodeling of global, rather than compartmentalised neuronal parameters.

In contrast to this exposition, in the classical associative synaptic model of plasticity the synapse signals to the core and the core signals back to the relevant synapse. Therefore a synapse needs a tag to be identified. This "synaptic tag" hypothesis has been much discussed, but turned out not to be experimentally verifiable [79, 76, 58]. Instead we suggest that expression at the core affects the whole neuron, where localized plasticity can be handled by the combination of a global bias term from the core and local parameter setting. Since there is local plasticity (usually fluctuating) which is direct and immediate at each synaptic site (postsynaptic or presynaptic), neural connections can be differentially regulated in spite of the global bias term. The local sites can signal to the global core. The central, global site signals back to all sites. There is spatial and temporal integration of signals happening in the intermediate layer and being present at the core.

3 Vertical Computation

In this section we describe a number of adaptive processes that are being performed by vertical computation. Our model of horizontal-vertical computation consists of spiking activity distributed over a group of connected neuron (spatio-temporal patterns), which are reflected as signals at a neuron or neuronal site (like a spine). In the model, the processing of the signals is determined by external, internal and core parameters. If a signal produces a match with the dendritic structure of the neuron, the neuron spikes. Neuronal spiking transmits a signal to all other neurons which are connected by synapses. However, transmission of signals by itself is not sufficient to result in adaptation or parameter change. It may lead to adaptation if calcium transients and other internal parameters fit.

What is important, is that each neuron represents a specially designed processor, which will process information according to its own program. Such a program can be generic for a neuronal type ("naive" neuron) or it can be acquired and specific ("mature" neuron). It can be re-programmed by the complex control structures of protein signaling and in this way generate an new, adapted internal model.

Neurons have been set up by evolution with their own genetic footprint, and it is important to realize that any neural computation is performed by a set of heterogeneous neurons which are adaptive but retain their cellular identity. Evolution has done the 'main work' in establishing neuronal types. For instance, there are pyramidal neurons, a type of excitatory projection neuron, and then there are specifically cortical vs. hippocampal pyramidal neurons, and for cortical neurons there are surface-layer vs. deep-layer pyramidal neurons, and as we increasingly learn, there are even a number of genetically distinct deep-layer cortical pyramidal neurons [15], etc. For a model, the evolutionary processes do not need to be re-created directly (even though that could be very interesting). Instead, neuronal types could be set up from a set of pre-established neuron models. Each of these neurons then has a genetic make-up and provides a type-specific programmable unit, where programming serves to individualize the response.

There are a number of mechanisms which fulfill the idea of a programmable internal system. Internal signaling can cause activation or de-activation of a dendritic branch, it can reset presynaptic vesicle pools (e.g. by cAMP-dependence), it guides spine maturation and spine decay, and it performs spatial integration on the spine (e.g. AMPA reservoirs on

the spine shaft moving to the spine synapse [6]). There are local buffers (cAMKII), and in the cytoplasm, there are timed delays, queues, feedback cycles which suppress a signal or enhance it, there is spatial integration over several compartments ([93]), antagonistic signaling [82] and overflow switches [83].

The intracellular signaling system passes a signal to outputs in the membrane or actuators in the nucleus after performing computation. The cytoplasm acts as a shared access system for the local compartments and protein complexes, routing inputs from many dendritic compartments to a single nuclear compartment. (The axonal system is not further described here). The output of processing guides signals from a spatially distributed system to a queued system or feeds it back to the membrane. Here we offer a list of examples for programmable computations in neurons that have been investigated before:

1. In [83], we showed how a strong signal at a G-protein coupled receptor together with high protein expression at a target pathway (which is not usually involved in signaling by this receptor) results in activation of the target, a different pathway from the canonical one ('transactivation'). The result is signaling by a pathway with several new effectors which happens only under special conditions. We called this an *overflow switch*, as a motif in computation, emphasizing the mechanical control aspect of internal signalling.
2. A common, ubiquitous motif in protein interactions is *antagonistic signaling*. This happens when an input is linked to an output by two antagonistic pathways (positive and negative) [82], such as D1/D2-type dopaminergic signaling, or beta/alpha-adrenergic signaling. It allows re-scaling of inputs which vary over a large scale, compressing multiple orders of magnitude to a single-scale value. Also, antagonistic signaling allows for peak transients when one pathway is slightly faster than the other. These features are useful basic properties for any system that handles signals.
3. Molecular abundances are important not just for establishing (high expression) or removing (low expression) connections between pathways as in [83], they also dictate the *temporal execution* of the biochemical reactions underlying intracellular signaling [88]. High expression means that reactions are fast and homeostatic endpoints are reached in short times. When protein expression is lower overall, internal reactions are slowed down and signals are processed sluggishly. In principle, this allows neurons to act at different time scales. This could be especially useful in situations where neural transmission (fast, high protein expression) is coupled with plasticity (slow, low protein expression).
4. To analyze biochemical reaction networks, we employed a *transfer function* approximation for G protein coupled receptor (GPCR) regulation (such as for mGLU, GABA-B, monoamines, neuropeptides), in [89]. Transfer functions allow to generate essentially (context-dependent) look-up tables for endpoints of internal parameters after external signaling. This is the basis for machine learning of internal parameters. It provides a suitable basis for internal computations and new values based on changes in protein expression.
5. Using the many types of buffers available, we can achieve *re-sorting of signals* in time. During buffering, spatial and temporal integration happen together. A typical example is the protein CaMKII, which buffers calcium by autocatalytic activity, and which releases calcium after some time – depending on the activation status of each buffer molecule. This allows to create a reverse calcium sequence, relative to the location received within the cytoplasm, and therefore provides a basis for a queued access to nuclear transcription.
6. The sequence reversal motif, i.e. the reordering of signals in time (with the help of buffers, which store a signal and release it later, vs. later signals which pass through immediately), together with other motifs, allows to produce *canonical shapes*, potentially making it easier for other calcium-receptive pathways to process the signal. A sequence of synaptic inputs, which are sorted and combined from their spatial distribution into larger components (e.g. like a bit code which is translated into 'words'), could provide a shape of signal that can be easily read.
7. There is mRNA-mediated plasticity at the spine, which remains localized [98] or spreads *locally* along the dendrite. But if sufficient signals combine and the nucleus is involved, we assume that neural remodeling affects the membrane *globally*, not just an activated synapse. Instead of tags at potentiated synapses which direct nuclear transcription products to those synapses, a simpler mechanism may be in place, a global effect or bias term that results from nuclear read-out and is combined with fast-fluctuating local plasticity. Then synaptic structure is a combination of a global (nucleus-based) and a local (spine, synapse) term.

To summarize, outside signals are received by external parameters and activate a program on the internal system which determines the regulation for external membrane properties. The internal computational system responds to signals and produces outcomes [84]. The system of computation, that filters and temporally re-sorts signals, that combines signals, and releases them is a programmable and re-programmable system. The system contains parameters which program its functionality. It has no memory but it can be reset by the core system. To re-program the system requires

new transcription or mRNA translation. To investigate the power of such systems, explicit programming, agent-based, dynamical systems as well as machine learning techniques are suitable.

4 Combining Vertical and Horizontal Functions

The signal that the individual neuron receives is defined by the pattern, i.e. the spatio-temporal spiking distribution on the horizontal layer [91]. We can predict the signal at each neuron from the pattern, but the patterns are undergoing transformation by the neurons which carry the pattern (representational drift, [62, 51]. To simplify discussions of horizontal interactions, we assume neurons interact solely by spiking, which means neurons tell each other just how active they are by their spiking patterns. Neural transmission, the horizontal interaction between neurons, is then explicitly determined by external membrane parameters. They can be local to the synapse (e.g. AMPA, NMDA receptors), affect a dendrite (e.g. ion channels), or be restricted to neuromodulatory activation (e.g. different kinds of GPCRs), or other factors. These spiking patterns appear as spatio-temporal patterns (STPs) over a group of neurons.

For each neuron there is a set of external and internal parameters that defines the state of the neuron. External parameters adapt to and are adapted by outside signals and receive feedback through the horizontal layer. Patterns are generated by structured groups of neurons, in particular microcircuits (ensembles), which are made up of similar neural types, or neural loops which run through several different brain areas, and are composed of different neural types. It is an interesting hypothesis rarely investigated that for the functioning of the neuron, evolution has developed neurons to be as independent as possible from outside signals. This is a question of efficiency of computation, where communication slows computation. We also assume an internal generative model which defines a default set for the membrane parameters undergoing constant fluctuations. Some reflection of this lies in the high stochasticity of the neuron [51, 53, 67]. Possibly, the neuron is mostly independent and stable as a processor, and the capacity for outside signals to create significant change - beyond the random walk fluctuations at the membrane [101] - is quite limited. It is definitely not automatic with each spike or transmission event. In this sense then the neuron is autonomous, even though outside signals can re-program its state.

Horizontal interactions can be seen as a system with massively parallel search for matches of signals to neurons. If there is a match, the neuron's spiking activity changes (in most cases it increases), a subgraph of connected neurons is activated, and new patterns emerge. Since STPs rely on membrane (synaptic and non-synaptic) properties of neurons which are subject to parameter adaptation, STPs undergo constant transformation. Thus a pattern is transformed via the signals it produces at individual neurons. While patterns are formed, new perceptual input may be suppressed. Local neural adaptations - for instance by internal parameters - allow to adjust the horizontal pattern. Possibly as a result the pattern better matches to existing stored templates. In this way a pattern could become adapted to existing knowledge.

We assume that internal memorization may be coordinated across a neuronal group, an ensemble. We use "strain" for an objective function which is related both to high spiking activity and to synchronization/de-synchronization. To compute strain, one could use a normalized value to measure excitation (taking peaks and temporal spacing ("bursting") into account) and a measure for synchronization (by co-occurrence of spikes, or membrane potential fluctuations). Only under high strain may we assume vertical computation to be initiated. The objective function builds up in the horizontal plane and gets resolved by adjusting parameters in vertical computation. Now parameter adaptations (via vertical internalization/externalization) allow a return to a homeostatically well-adjusted horizontal spatio-temporal pattern regime of low strain. Within a horizontal structure focal areas of high activation, such as resulting from sensory input, may be described as experiencing high "strain". This indicates that signal information is to be internalized, or that there is an opportunity to externalize information to reduce strain. A neuron can "absorb" strain from the representation. High strain may cause a network to store information internally and remove it from the external membrane, or vice versa to read out parameters so as to reduce activations.

In the short term, control structures using internal parameters in the membrane-near intracellular layer influence external membrane properties directly and immediately. Spatial resolution is kept. This is fast adaptation of neural membrane properties. Additionally, membrane-near control structures select strong signals, which are internalized and maintained (e.g. with the help of calcium buffers) without additional effects on neural transmission. When the signal reaches cytoplasmic protein complexes and the nucleus, spatial resolution is lost and global neural remodelling occurs. This is lasting plasticity.

We may distinguish between the responses of naive and mature neurons, or neurons with default control structures vs. neurons with a learned internal parameter structure. This is a concept that needs some explanation. Naive neurons exist with default configurations, possibly with random elements, and patterned exposure to signals makes them acquire a specific generative internal-external model which reflects the neuron's experience and expectation. This is a 'mature' neuron, or, rather, it is a process of maturation. Such a neuron may still learn and re-learn, and possibly even re-set to the naive state under exceptional circumstances. An outside "raw" signal has a different effect for a naive neuron - where it

is imprinted - or a mature neuron where it is matched or non-matched. In the naive neuron there is no individualized control structure to filter the signal. Internalization involves setting-up a copy of the external parameter set as the basis of a generative model or a "prior" for later processing [91]. In a mature neuron, the signal is filtered and matched to the existing parameter set. A naive site will store or read in the next value, a mature site already contains a value and is protected against overwrite. However, maturity could be a graded property, and a neuron could be 'chimeric' with respect to maturity. For instance spines could be either naive or mature on the same neuron, and a dendrite 'bit-coded' for grade of maturity.

Neuromodulation has an interesting role in that it codes for cellular identity in a combinatorial fashion [86]. It can thus serve as labeling, both for neurons and connections (nodes and edges of a graph structure). Such labeling is extremely useful because it allows for constrained inferences [81]. For instance, a dopamine D2 receptor may adjust GIRK channels and subsequently the spike pattern reflects hyperpolarized membranes at affected (labeled) neurons – a temporary change (which requires a dopamine signal).

Overall, we anticipate a network of processors with their own individual memory, intimately connected by bit-type signals, participating in low-dimensional representational configurations, to offer a highly flexible and sophisticated framework suitable for complex computations of the kind that humans perform [32, 55].

5 Problems and Applications

5.1 Multiple Temporal Scales

The ability of short-term signals to produce an internal response which lasts over minutes or hours is dependent on the internal parameters which guide the signal into the core. Within the core, epigenetic mechanisms decide what happens with the signals accessing the DNA.

How do we link short-term signals over milliseconds or seconds, with the long-lasting plasticity exhibited at neurons, happening over minutes or even hours? The dynamics of plasticity is usually simply subsumed under the concepts of either short-term or long-term (synaptic) plasticity [25], without a clear understanding how the temporal levels interact - this points to a larger problem [10]. The temporal structure of filtering of outside signals and integration with stored information is not well explored, neither in experiments, nor in theoretical models. The neuron receives many signals, usually with fast durations (synaptic activations are on the order of 10-100ms, some of the longest durations have been measured for dopamine levels during feeding, for up to 10 minutes). Internal adaptations take at least minutes and access to core parameters may take hours or even days during which the system still adapts.

A neuron is a system with fast fluctuations of signals (milliseconds-seconds) at the periphery where outside signals arrive and are selected or filtered, and slow processes (hours) in the core, where long-term information (genes) is transcribed, and genetic programs activated. From the periphery to the core, each step happens at a slower scale. It is an unusual type of computational system which operates along those principles. Presumably, the system is remarkable in that it can select individual short-term signals as highly relevant and transform them into long-lasting information, while at the same time filtering out very many other signals which are less relevant or redundant. Often it is assumed that a neuron collects all evidence and uses it statistically (e.g. sums it at its synapses). While such statistical screening may happen, the decisive function that the neuron is built for is to create lasting memory of individual brief events.

Dynamic processes that span many different time scales – from milliseconds to minutes, hours, or days – are in general difficult to model, and difficult to understand [74, 103, 97]. A simple mechanism for a multiscale situation is to use a modular system, where each module operates on its own time-scale and results are passed between the modules at appropriate times [105]. For instance, from a fast module an integrated term could be passed on, whenever a computation reaches an end-point (at irregular times) and from a slow module a changing bias term could be passed to the fast modules at regular intervals. This could be applied to the external, internal and core systems.

5.2 Programmable elements

A weighted neural network is a simple data structure (graph) with only one degree of freedom (weights) for recording past experience. Accordingly, it mostly stores data (or data-classification pairs) and generalizes by interpolation (or extrapolation). In contrast, a horizontal-vertical network is a network of processors with a large number of parameters sorted by function, dynamics, and structure (external, internal, core). This system can do more than adapt to outside signals and store traces of them. It can (a) select and filter, i.e. ignore many outside signals if there is no internal reinforcement and (b) it can also self-program, i.e. self-adapt its internal processing structure. The self-programming mechanism relies essentially on a stream of outside signals (data), and feedback from the slow center to the fast periphery to handle the signals (Figure 2).

Here are a number of features which define the capacity for self-programming for a neuron within a network of processors:

- re-programming the system for external and internal parameters by genetic control of protein abundances
- preset ranges for adaptation of external parameters by outside signals
- manipulating the rate of change (slow and fast) for parameters to address the stability-flexibility dichotomy
- existence of programs in the genetic core which can be enacted *in toto* and allow complex morphological adaptation such as spine growth, dendrite remodelling, axonal branching

Internal signaling networks, which are a type of biochemical reaction networks, guarantee a return to homeostasis [13, 89, 11]. This means that these signaling networks have no memory of their own. They react to signals, but then return to their preset values. They are thus protected against signal-based adaptation or signal-based memory. However, there are the protein abundances which re-program the system and which are under control of another system, an outside system, namely RNA translation, or DNA transcription. So the system itself would be designed to not have any memory of the actual processing it performs. This means that it acts as a processing layer sending signals into the 'actuators', the membrane or the nucleus, where signals are then absorbed, (e.g. in the histone layer) or may cause further DNA transcriptions after considerable time delay. These may re-program the system.

What can be programmed? The system has a number of control parameters available which govern neural transmission, i.e. neuronal behavior in interaction with other neurons on the horizontal plane. These parameters code for membrane excitability, i.e. firing threshold, membrane resting potential; afterdepolarization/ afterhyperpolarization, i.e. refractory reset properties; spike latency, axonal delay, degree of myelination [14], etc. They set the firing rate and the capacity for synchronization. The placement of GABA-A [68], and glutamate receptors influences synaptic transmission, and the capacity of the dendrites to route excitations to the soma. There are other membrane properties which also constitute programmable elements but which influence neural transmission in a more subtle way. NM receptors or GPCRs (including GABA-B, mGLU) which are regulated in response to ligand availability activate internal parameters (e.g. $G_{\beta\gamma}$, cAMP) from membrane receptors. These can modulate membrane properties directly by a fast feedback mechanism. They also signal to the nucleus, directly (PKA), or indirectly (MAPK, ERK) using the internal parameter system [83, 89] and in this way provide a significant part of the filtering system for outside signals.

Recently it has been argued that novel behavioral signals may affect at first epigenetic features, i.e. histones, while only after repetition there is read-out of DNA [104]. In this sense a naive neuron may at first have only its accessibility of DNA being affected by signals, awaiting further confirmation to actually read out DNA programs. Programming a neuron's core identity may take several steps (Figure 2). In the end, a complex program guides the actions that re-define a neuron's morphology or alter its membrane composition. For instance, the core contains programs that grow or mature a spine, produce and insert neuromodulatory receptors, move new AMPA receptors to the postsynaptic density ([66]), convert silent NMDA receptors, or balance and co-regulate ion channels [21].

To build a generative model for the external parameter set of a neuron, internal parameters can exchange or restore external parameters (e.g. they modulate receptor endocytosis followed by insertion or ubiquitination). They can protect parameters against overwrite (e.g. by placing Sk-channels next to calcium channels/AMPA/NMDA receptors [41]). They can also modify receptor complexes (e.g. co-localization of D1/NMDA receptors[4]). The internally regulated, targeted placement of neuromodulator receptors allows to switch between several modalities on short time scales (seconds to minutes) by activation of neuromodulatory signals [81]. The precise mechanisms by which the neuron self-programs its many features are still a matter of further research.

5.3 Knowledge structures

In the brain, memory items are linked together to form knowledge structures. Each neuron belongs to a constellation of neurons ('ensembles' [31, 48]), which also may reach into different brain areas (e.g. cortical-hippocampal constellations). These can be described as sub-graphs in a 'knowledge graph' [36, 99]. A sub-graph can be compressed as a single neuron [91], creating a 'concept' as an abstraction of entities [80]. This involves internalization of information and adaptation of neuronal identity. The abstraction that happens for concept formation may extend from a small contribution to a stored schema to the complete reconstruction of a spatio-temporal pattern, such as an event memory. Most importantly, so-called semantic memory [16] (or factual memory) is the result of abstraction and concept formation. By belief propagation or similar techniques there may be enmeshment of the sub-graphs to more complex graphs. This allows to build higher-order structures, for instance, by re-assigning connections in the graph or by vertical externalization to restore patterns.(Fig.)

Decisive for structure building or knowledge abstraction to work are processes of different stability, such as stable concept neurons combined with flexible graph connectivity. For example, during a certain spatio-temporal pattern a

Figure 2: Building blocks for self-programming of neurons. Outside signals (Data) are processed by external parameters (EXT) which interact with internal parameters (INT). The EXT/INT system changes over time. The decisive feature for adaptation is the feedback between the core and internal systems. Note that data are maximally separated from the core system.

network state might consist of a distribution of synaptic AMPA channels, K⁺ and Ca-K⁺ channels over its neurons. Key (engram or 'concept') neurons for this pattern could employ overwrite protection, and therefore keep their parameter sets stable (without further adaptations at their sites). The flexible neurons, which do not use protection, would form a background of fluctuating, nearly random parameter sets.

In [91] we presented a model where a spatio-temporal spiking pattern is compressed into a couple of neurons with the highest mutual information with the pattern. It was then shown that stimulating these neurons is sufficient for re-activating the pattern. The activation of the key neurons would restore the spatio-temporal pattern independent of further learning [91]. In this way, parts of the horizontal structure (the pattern) become encapsulated into single neurons and these can be stimulated so that they unfold the spatio-temporal pattern on a network with background activity.

When a network exhibits a spatio-temporal spiking pattern, its corresponding signals are matched to stored models at individual neurons. A generative model consists to a large part of the neuron's connections, its dendritic integration properties and also other short-term stable external membrane parameters. The generative neural model, defined by its parameters, is being matched to the set of signals it receives. If a neuron receives signals that match its model, it spikes and it produces a significant calcium transient as marker of the spiking event. Adaptation, after selection and filtering, is performed by updating "priors" to signal-based "posteriors", and by optimizing the complexity of the models, which can be pruned by linking parameters.

In this way, the spatio-temporal spiking pattern starts a massively parallel search for matching neurons. For each matching neuron - typically in a sparse distribution - a sequence of new activations on the network follows. Matching neurons activate subnetworks, or ensembles of other neurons, to complete the pattern (horizontal computing). New patterns are created in an operation similar to drawing inferences from data. The upshot is that horizontal computing can be likened to operations on a knowledge graph, as long as the nodes contain their own internal information and adaptation.

6 Discussion

From a cognitive and behavioral perspective we know that episodic memory is not a reversible operation where a blank slate is inscribed and wiped again, but an operation where permanent changes occur when memories are stored. A developmental trajectory exists from neonate to juvenile to adult to aged individual. Only a fraction of events is stored with completeness. Much information is not kept and deemed not worth keeping. In episodic memory, many representations of events undergo abstraction and become part of a complex (schema) that they add to in small ways. Often, information that is sufficiently represented by existing knowledge is merely summed or discarded.

In a very general way, neuronal plasticity can be seen as a form of difference learning between stored information and new, incoming signals. This is also known as “predictive” or “generative learning”. Here we outlined a model with external parameters at the membrane, which guide transmission of information, with internal parameters, hidden from interactions, which store and process information and are capable of re-setting external values, and a core system that programs and re-programs the parameter system. The difference between outside signals and internal information drives adaptation and forces a system, such as a neuron, to remain an open system with respect to its environment, i.e. a system which lacks the properties of an algorithmic or formally ‘closed’ system. Memory management is central in such a system, to ensure consistency, promote signal loss where appropriate [90, 87], and prevent ‘catastrophic forgetting’ [35, 72].

The main problem with the synaptic hypothesis is that adjusting weights in graphs has weak expressive power. Treating neurons as adjustable activation functions improves efficiency of implementation considerably, but does not extend the expressive power of the system [85, 50, 96]. While such systems can store data well, they don’t function for more complex hierarchical knowledge and action plans, like language generation [43]. A mathematical theory of the expressive power of various neuronal representation systems is still lacking, to my knowledge. This would involve comparing purely horizontal to vertical-horizontal models.

The synaptic theory of memory also experiences a paradox since synapses are units with high turnover [67, 29]. This means that information cannot remain physically located at the synapses long-term without being lost or overwritten. Various schemes have been suggested to counteract this problem [29]. We showed that neurons as processors operate with graded stability (from outside to inside), a principle which seems very intuitive and sound. 3. Memorization involves transforming transient, potentially repeating information into stable information elements. Axonal/dendritic morphology must in this case also be regarded as a stable, core component, since it requires core-mediated programs for alteration. The peculiar nature of the neuronal cell as a processing device - concentric abstraction of temporal depth - is probably due to this unique requirement of providing short-term adaptation, long-term stability and the capacity to store information into increasingly stable formats (3). Types of neurons in different brain areas, defined by genetics and the product of evolutionary learning, are essentially stable, and they form part of a background structure. Any neural system must contain elements with high stability - which provide the backbone of the knowledge structure and are protected against change - and elements which flexibly adjust to current conditions. The stability-flexibility trade-off is probably at the center of the capacity of brains to build structured representations, subject to modifications (ART).

Many diseases of the brain relate to processes, molecules and interactions that cannot be captured adequately with the concept of synaptic plasticity. For instance, it was recently found that ketamine drives genetic expression of the KCNQ2 channel, which increases the I_M (K+) current [59, 95, 49]. In hippocampus this reduces bursting and lack of reset after spike firing, by reducing the afterdepolarization (ADP); but it also reduces spontaneous spiking at the excitatory synapse. It is possible that this latter effect transmits the long-lasting anti-depressant effect of single-dose ketamine [1]. Here a one-time increase of the genetic expression of an ion channel provides behavioral changes for many weeks. These type of results are easy to incorporate into a model of the horizontal-vertical type but not a synaptic weight adjustment model. It is important to realize that remembering is also a biochemical event. Activation of neurons leads to specific activations via long-term connections into deep brain regions (neural ‘loop’ structure). This connection may mean that a cocktail of neurochemicals (monoamines, neuropeptides, hormones etc.) is released.

We notice an important advance of the proposed theoretical model - as a horizontal-vertical model - is to bridge the divide between theoretical neuroscience, artificial intelligence and disease models. While small-scale models of disease processes exist (refs), there is an unmet need for brain theories and derivative models with actual functionality (AI), which model cellular processes exhibited by the neuron, and adequately capture their disruption within a disease process.

Horizontal-vertical integration models can be considered a substantial innovation, especially compared to associative weight adjustment models. They use neuron models with internal memory to build complex processor networks, combining data and experiments from electrophysiology and molecular biology. The proposed neuron model allows to realize self-programming of neurons and building complex models of cognition. The brain, of course, has many

Figure 3: The neuron - here drawn as a prototypical cell - acts as a processor which receives fast signals and responds with fluctuations on different temporal planes: the membrane is fast, and the core is slow. There is an intermediate zone. This can be seen as an original solution to the flexibility-stability problem in information storage and processing.

additional components, such as the capillary and glymphatic networks, glia cells, and the signals that pass the blood-brain barrier. In the future more comprehensive brain models may encompass such additional components.

7 Conclusion

The neuron is a highly specialized cell type, strongly compartmentalized with extensive axons and dendrites. Each compartment, dendritic or axonal, connects directly and specifically to other neurons. For this reason, there has always been a strong focus within neuroscience on the synapse as a specialized connective element between neurons, with its postsynaptic density protein composition, and its presynaptic vesicle release mechanism. This has led to theoretical neuroscience focusing on adjusting synaptic weights as the main memory mechanism. But by now the experimental literature on neuronal plasticity is vast, and synapses make up only a small part of it. Intrinsic forms of plasticity via ion channels and NM receptors are well-known and have been researched in great detail ([106, 60, 22, 92, 69, 33, 82, 85, 102]). The vertical, internal dimension of the neuron with its intracellular signaling network and the nuclear processes, genetic and epigenetic, has particular significance in the fields of psychopharmacology and disease modeling. But the development of a theoretical framework, linking those aspects of neural plasticity, has been missing. We have begun to fill the void by re-thinking the concept of neural plasticity from the perspective of the individual neuron. We argue that even synaptic plasticity is incompletely understood when placed outside of the context of cellular functioning.

Purely horizontal models with weight adaptation, like current neural network models, can only be programmed by input. That is very restrictive. Huge networks with billions of parameters are needed to solve simple problems by brute-force massive storage. Those restrictions are systematic and mathematically explainable, since the expressive power of networks with adjustable weights is weak. A programmable memory at each neuronal site allows for more complex and interesting operations. For instance, patterns from the horizontal plane can get stored into a small set of dedicated neurons for a particular problem. Such models may then be used to build complex knowledge structures.

We believe that the "third wave of AI" will have to employ some kind of horizontal-vertical brain model to make use of the opportunities of linking intracellular intelligence with large-scale neuron modeling to achieve a truly intelligent,

self-programmable system. An immediate challenge will be to create models which run in a self-contained way, and build up internal structures from the initial set-up and the processing of input patterns.

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